

Thermostabilization of firefly luciferase by *in vivo* directed evolution

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Abstract

Firefly luciferase is widely used in a number of areas of biotechnology and molecular biology. However, rapid inactivation of wild-type luciferases at elevated temperatures often hampers their application. A simple non-lethal *in vivo* screening scheme was used to identify thermostable mutants of luciferase in *E. coli* colonies. This scheme allowed to carry out each cycle of mutagenesis in a rapid and efficient manner. Four rounds of directed evolution were conducted on a part of the gene coding for amino acid residues 130–390 of *Luciola mingrelica* luciferase. The resultant mutant designated 4TS (LmiTS) had a half-life of 10 h at 42°C, which is 65-fold higher compared with the wild-type luciferase. Moreover, the mutant 4TS showed a 1.9-fold increase in specific activity, 5.7-fold reduction of K_M for ATP, and a higher temperature optimum compared with the wild-type enzyme. 4TS contains eight mutations, four of which are suggested to be mainly responsible for the enhancement of thermostability: R211L, A217V, E356K, and S364C. Thus, directed evolution with non-lethal colony screening for *in vivo* bioluminescence activity proved to be an effective and efficient approach for increasing thermal stability of luciferase while retaining high catalytic activity.

Keywords: firefly luciferase, *Luciola mingrelica*, directed evolution, random mutagenesis, thermal stability

Introduction

Bioluminescence is widely distributed in nature and can be found in bacteria, dinoflagellates, fungi, insects, coelenterates, fish, mollusks, and others. “Luciferase” is a generic term for oxygenases that catalyze the oxidation of a substrate, “luciferin”, which is accompanied by the emission of light (Hastings *et al.*, 2003; Herring, 1987). However, different bioluminescence systems are a result of convergent evolution, so that the corresponding luciferase proteins are not homologous, and their luciferins belong to many unrelated chemical classes. Firefly luciferase (EC 1.13.12.7) catalyzes a two-step oxidation of firefly luciferin (LH₂) in the presence of

ATP, Mg²⁺, and molecular oxygen which results in the emission of a photon and the release of oxyluciferin (LO), AMP, CO₂, and pyrophosphate (Fraga, 2008; Hosseinkhani, 2011). Due to the high quantum yield of its bioluminescence (Niwa *et al.*, 2010), high catalytic efficiency, and substrate specificity, firefly luciferase is widely used in ATP assays and as a reporter gene in molecular imaging (Lundin, 2000; Prescher and Contag, 2010; Roda *et al.*, 2009). This enzyme is also a promising tool for molecular sensing of different analytes and protein-protein interactions (Binkowski *et al.*, 2009), for real time detection of nucleic acid amplification (Gandelman *et al.*, 2010) and a label for immunoassays (Minekawa *et al.*,

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2009). However, insufficient stability of wild-type (WT) beetle luciferases at temperatures above 30°C often limits their applications demanding the development of thermostable forms of the enzyme (Branchini *et al.*, 2007; Li *et al.*, 2010).

Various approaches have been used to increase the thermostability of firefly luciferase. Improvements in stability at 37°C can be achieved by the addition of stabilizing compounds (Eriksson *et al.*, 2003; Moroz *et al.*, 2008), but the mutagenesis approach appears to be the most successful, especially a random one, since bioluminescence allows simple screening for residual activity. Several specific positions were discovered by random mutagenesis that significantly increased luciferase thermostability (Kajiyama and Nakano, 1993; Tisi *et al.*, 2002; White *et al.*, 1996). In these cases, a plate-based screening technique was used to identify thermostable mutants, and bioluminescence of bacterial colonies was detected by the use of X-ray film (Wood and DeLuca, 1987). However, in the later works an approach of site-directed mutagenesis became the most widespread. The positions identified earlier by random mutagenesis were further explored by site-directed mutagenesis and were used for the construction of multi-point mutants (Branchini *et al.*, 2007; Kitayama *et al.*, 2003; Tisi *et al.*, 2002). The 5-point mutant of *Photinus pyralis* luciferase (Ppl) showed a half-life of 11.5 hours at 37°C, a 44-fold improvement over WT (Branchini *et al.*, 2007). In several works the 3D-structure of firefly luciferase was used as a basis for rational design of thermostable mutants, namely, the mutagenesis of solvent exposed residues (Law *et al.*, 2006), the introduction of disulfide bonds (Imani *et al.*, 2010), and the comparative analysis of the selected residue microenvironment (Koksharov and Ugarova, 2011).

It should be noted that mutations effective for one firefly luciferase do not always lead to similar results when applied to other homologous luciferases. For example, the A217L substitution in most luciferases resulted in a fully active thermostable enzyme, but in the case of *Hotaria parvula* luciferase (Hpl) this mutation decreased activity to about 0.1% of the WT enzyme. While the E354R mutation increased thermostability of Ppl, the corresponding E356R substitution did not affect Hpl (Kitayama *et al.*, 2003). Thus, the use of homologous mutations and rational design for the construction of thermostable mutants has some limitations and may require broad study of potential substitutions because many of the designed mutations could be unsuccessful.

Firefly luciferase can be simply screened for its *in vivo*

bioluminescence activity (Wood and DeLuca, 1987), thus making a directed evolution approach the most promising. In this strategy multiple consecutive cycles of random mutagenesis and screening are used for an incremental increase of the required property of an enzyme. Directed evolution has been successfully applied to improve or change a wide range of enzyme properties such as expression level, enantioselectivity, substrate specificity, thermal stability, and activity in non-natural environments (Eijsink *et al.*, 2005; Kuchner and Arnold, 1997). However, there is only one example when this approach was used to increase the thermostability of firefly luciferase. The most stable firefly luciferase to date is a mutant of *Photuris pennsylvanica* luciferase obtained by directed evolution. It contains 28 substitutions and shows a half-life of about 27 h at 65°C (Wood and Hall, 1999; Wood *et al.*, 2007). In this case a sophisticated automatic robotic system was used for the screening procedure, thus possibly limiting a wide application of this technique. In this work we report a simple and efficient screening strategy that was successfully used to evolve a thermostable form of *Luciola mingrelica* luciferase (Lml).

WT Lml displays relatively low thermostability losing about 50% of activity within 50 minutes at 37°C. We used four consecutive rounds of random mutagenesis and screening to considerably improve thermostability of Lml without compromising its activity. Bioluminescent properties of luciferase and the ability of *E. coli* cells to withstand temperatures up to about 55°C (Jiang *et al.*, 2003) allowed us to identify thermostable mutants by a simple non-lethal *in vivo* screening of *E. coli* colonies producing mutant luciferases. *E. coli* cells remained viable after the screening procedure, so colonies could be picked directly from the plate screened, which eliminates the need for replica plates during primary screening of mutant libraries. Each cycle of mutagenesis was conducted in a rapid and efficient manner by the use of this scheme. The thermostability screening strategy described here is the simplest among reported in the literature, and can potentially be used to increase thermostability of any other promising beetle luciferase.

Materials and methods

Materials

Na-ATP, bovine serum albumin, dithiothreitol (DTT), yeast extract (cat. no. Y-0500) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, USA), D-luciferin was from Lumtek (Moscow,

Russia), TaqSE DNA polymerase was from Sibenzyme (Novosibirsk, Russia), Taq DNA polymerase and T4 DNA ligase were from Sileks (Moscow, Russia), oligonucleotide primers were obtained from Sintol (Moscow, Russia), bacto-tryptone was from Becton Dickinson (USA), lactose 1-hydrate was from Panreac (Montcada, Spain). Competent *E. coli* cells were prepared and transformed according to the method developed by Tu and coworkers (Tu *et al.*, 2005). All the reagents were of analytical grade, and solutions were prepared using Milli-Q water. The purified mutant Lml enzyme containing the substitution S118C was obtained earlier (Koksharov and Ugarova, 2008).

Random mutagenesis by error-prone PCR and mutant library construction

The pLR3 plasmid (GenBank No. HQ007051) which encodes *L. mingrelica* luciferase gene was constructed earlier (Koksharov and Ugarova, 2008). Random mutagenesis of the 785 base pair region flanked by XhoI and BglII restriction sites was performed by error-prone PCR (Cirino *et al.*, 2003). Primers 5'-GTATTCAGCTCGAGAAAAGGCTTACC-3' and 5'-GCTTGTGGTTTCTTAAGAATTTCTCTAATTAC-3' were used as forward and reverse primers, respectively. The PCR reaction mixture (50 μ l) contained 10 mM Tris-HCl (pH 8.3 at 25°C), 50 mM KCl, 7 mM MgCl₂, 0.2 mM MnCl₂, 0.2 mM dATP, 0.2 mM dGTP, 1 mM dCTP, 1 mM dTTP, 20 pmol of each primer, ~2 fmol of pLR3, and 2.5 units of Taq DNA-polymerase. PCR was performed with an automatic thermal cycler Tercik (DNA-Technology, Russia) under the following conditions: 95°C, 1 min; 25 cycles for 1 min at 94°C, 1.3 min at 53°C, 1 min at 72°C; then 10 min at 72°C. These conditions should lead to an error frequency of 2–3 substitutions or approximately one amino acid per 800 bp gene region (Miyazaki and Arnold, 1999). The mutagenic PCR product was gel purified by using the QIAEX II kit (Qiagen, Germany) and then digested with XhoI and BglII. This restriction product was gel purified and ligated into pLR3 previously treated with the same restriction enzymes. A typical ligation reaction (10 μ l final volume) contained ~20 ng insert, ~50 ng vector, 1x T4 DNA ligase buffer, 1 Weiss Unit T4 DNA ligase, and 5% w/v PEG-8000, and was incubated at 16°C for 1 hour. *E. coli* XL1-blue cells were transformed with the resultant mutant plasmids and plated onto Luria-Bertani (LB) agar supplemented with 100 μ g/ml ampicillin.

The pLR3 plasmid used in the 2nd–4th cycles contained the additional mutation Y35N resulting in green

bioluminescence of *E. coli* colonies compared with orange-yellow bioluminescence in the case of WT (Koksharov and Ugarova, 2008). The mutation Y35N was used to identify possible red-shifting mutants during a screening for *in vivo* bioluminescence. The most stable mutant obtained after the 4th cycle was later subcloned into the plasmid without the mutation Y35N for the subsequent expression and purification.

Thermostability screening

E. coli colonies harboring mutant luciferase genes were grown overnight at 37°C on LB agar plates supplemented with 100 g/ml ampicillin. The *in vivo* bioluminescence of the colonies was registered photographically according to the following protocol: plates were filled with a thin layer of 0.5 mM luciferin solution in 0.1 M Na-citrate buffer (pH 5.0), shaken in the dark room and photographed with the Canon PowerShot A530 digital camera (Canon, Malaysia). This step was performed quickly within 3–4 minutes. Prolonged incubation of the plate under the solution could result in partial washing away of colonies and lead to a cross-contamination. Then the luciferin solution was quickly discarded from the plates and the plates were heated at 50–55°C (depending on the cycle of mutagenesis) for 40 minutes in Certomat H incubation hood (Sartorius-BBI, Germany). After incubation the colonies were screened for residual activity by photographic registration of the *in vivo* bioluminescence as written above. The brightest colonies were picked and transferred onto two LB agar plates supplemented with 100 g/ml ampicillin. Several colonies carrying a parent form of luciferase (in a current cycle of mutagenesis) were also transferred onto these plates as a control. The colonies were grown overnight at 37°C and then stored at room temperature for 4–8 h. Then the colonies were screened for *in vivo* bioluminescence: one replica plate after the growth to compare the activity of the mutants and another replica plate after heating at 50–55°C for 40 minutes to identify the most thermostable mutant.

Expression and purification of luciferase

The WT and the mutant 4TS were cloned into the expression vector pETL7 (GenBank No. HQ007050) that was constructed earlier (Koksharov and Ugarova, 2011). The pETL7 plasmid encodes the luciferase protein with several differences as compared with the native enzyme: additional N-terminal sequence MASK- and the C-terminal AKM peptide

changed to the SGPVEHHHHHH sequence. The WT luciferase and the mutant 4TS were expressed as His₆-tagged proteins in *E. coli* BL21(DE3)CodonPlus cells according to the lactose-based autoinduction method (Studier, 2005). *E. coli* cells containing pETL7 plasmid were plated on LB agar containing 100 µg/ml ampicillin and incubated overnight at 37°C. 3 ml of LB supplemented with 100 µg/ml ampicillin and 1% glucose were inoculated with 1–3 colonies. The cultures were grown for 3–4 h on a shaker at 37°C, 180 rpm, until the cell suspension became turbid ($A_{600} = 0.3–0.9$). 1 L flasks with 200 ml of ZYP-5052 medium (Studier, 2005) supplemented with 100 µg/ml ampicillin were inoculated with the cell cultures so that $A_{600} = 0.0024$. The 200 ml cultures were grown on a shaker for 2 h at 37°C, 180 rpm or until the suspension became slightly turbid ($A_{600} = 0.2–0.5$). Then the cultures were incubated at 23°C for 15–18 h until $A_{600} = 5–9$. The cells were harvested by centrifugation at 5500 g and 4°C. The cell pellet was resuspended in 18–20 ml of 20 mM Naphosphate buffer containing 0.5 M NaCl, pH 7.5 (buffer HB) supplemented with 20 mM imidazole and 0.5% Triton X-100. The cells were lysed by sonication, and the debris was removed by centrifugation at 39000g and 4°C for 30 min. Proteins were further purified using a Ni-affinity 1 ml HiTrap FF column (GE HealthCare, Sweden). The supernatants (~20 ml) were loaded on a 1 ml Ni-IDA column and washed with 20–40 ml HB buffer containing 20 mM imidazole. The enzymes were eluted with HB buffer containing 300 mM imidazole. Chromatography was performed at 4°C. The luciferase solution obtained was further supplemented with EDTA (0.5 M, pH 8.0) to 2 mM and DTT (1 M in 10 mM Na-acetate buffer, pH 5.2) to 1 mM. For the removal of imidazole and the long-term storage, the enzymes were transferred by gel-filtration to 50 mM Tris-acetate buffer (pH 7.3) containing 100 mM Na₂SO₄, 2 mM EDTA (buffer GF). The luciferase solution obtained was further supplemented with 1 mM DTT and stored at –80°C. The protein concentration was determined prior to the addition of DTT by absorbance at 280 nm using an absorption coefficient of $A^{1\text{cm}} = 0.56$ for 0.1% solution of Lml, which was calculated based on the amino acid sequence of the protein (Gasteiger *et al.*, 2005).

Bioluminescence spectra

Bioluminescence spectra were obtained using a Perkin-Elmer LS50B luminescence spectrometer operated in the “bioluminescence” mode at a slit width of 10 nm as described previously (Koksharov and Ugarova, 2008). Data were

automatically corrected for the spectral response of the R928 photomultiplier tube using the FL WinLab software. Generally, the spectra selected for the analysis were recorded when decrease in intensity during the recording interval did not exceed 5%. If the emission was unstable due to the luciferase inactivation at high temperatures, the spectra were corrected for the decrease of intensity during the time of measurement. Spectra were smoothed using Quadratic Golay–Savitzky filter in FL WinLab software.

Enzyme activity and kinetic parameters

Luciferase activity was determined using FB12 luminometer (Zylux, USA). Maximal intensity of the light emitted during the enzymatic reaction at saturating concentrations of substrates (flash height–based activity assay) was used as a measure of the luciferase activity. The cuvette contained 0.35 ml of 1.7 mM ATP in 50 mM Tris-acetate buffer (pH 7.8) containing 2 mM EDTA, 10 mM MgSO₄ (buffer AB) and 5 µl of luciferase solution. Assay was initiated by injecting 0.15 ml of 0.5 mM luciferin in the same buffer and the bioluminescence intensity was registered at room temperature (20–25°C). The final concentrations of LH₂ and ATP were 0.15 and 1.2 mM, respectively, in a volume of 0.5 ml. An analyzed luciferase solution (1–100 µg/ml) was quickly diluted by the factor of 10² or 10⁴ just before the measurement so that the bioluminescence intensity values fall within the dynamic range of the luminometer. Activity was expressed in relative light units (RLU/s) of the luminometer. No corrections were applied for the spectral response of the photomultiplier tube (PMT). ATP concentration was calculated using a molar extinction coefficient of 15400 M⁻¹cm⁻¹ at 259 nm in buffer AB. LH₂ concentration was calculated using a molar extinction coefficient of 18200 M⁻¹cm⁻¹ at 385 nm in 0.5 M Na-carbonate buffer, pH 11.5 (Morton *et al.*, 1969).

The values of K_M and V_{max} for LH₂ and ATP were determined from bioluminescence activity assays. The concentration of one substrate was maintained at saturation and the concentration of the other substrate was varied (0.012–1.2 mM ATP and 0.014–0.5 mM LH₂). 13 g/ml stock luciferase solution was used in the experiment that was further diluted 100-fold during the activity assay. A neutral filter was placed in the cuvette compartment of the luminometer so that bioluminescence intensity values fall within the dynamic range of the luminometer. Kinetic constants were calculated from Michaelis–Menten graph using non-linear regression in Origin

7.5 software (OriginLab, USA).

Kinetics of thermal inactivation

The solution of the purified luciferase (13 g/ml) was prepared in 50 mM Tris-acetate buffer containing 20 mM MgSO₄, 2 mM EDTA, 0.2 mg/ml BSA, pH 7.8 (TsB1 buffer) or in 50 mM Na-phosphate buffer containing 410 mM (NH₄)₂SO₄, 2 mM EDTA, 0.2 mg/ml BSA, pH 7.8 (TsB2 buffer). This solution was then stored on ice at 0°C. In the case of fast inactivation (half-life < 30 min) aliquots of 50 µl were placed in 8 thin wall 0.5 ml microtubes. Each tube was used for the activity testing separately. In the case of slow inactivation (half-life > 30 min) 1.5 ml of luciferase solution was placed in a 1.7 ml microtube. Microtubes were incubated at the temperature studied (37–55°C). At given times a tube with a 50 µl aliquot or 50 µl volume was removed and cooled on ice for at least 15 min prior to the activity assay. A neutral filter was placed in the cuvette compartment of the luminometer so that bioluminescence intensity values fall within the dynamic range of the luminometer. The enzyme activity was expressed as a percentage of the initial activity. Half-lives were calculated using the first-order reaction rate constants obtained from semi-logarithmic plots of the percentage of activity versus time.

Temperature optimum of activity

The temperature optimum of activity was estimated as follows. The solution of the purified luciferase (5×10⁻⁵ mg/ml) was prepared in 50 mM Tris-acetate buffer (pH 7.8) containing 10 mM MgSO₄, 2 mM EDTA, 0.2 mg/ml BSA and was stored on ice at 0°C. 2 ml of 50 mM Tris-acetate buffer (pH 7.8) containing 2 mM EDTA, 10 mM MgSO₄ and 1.7 mM ATP was placed into cuvettes and incubated in a water thermostat for 10 min at the temperature studied. A cuvette was removed from the thermostat, 10 µl of luciferase solution was immediately added into the cuvette, quickly mixed and placed in the luminometer standing at room temperature. Then 90 µl of 4.5 mM luciferin in the same buffer was immediately injected and the bioluminescence intensity was measured. The integrated intensity during the first 20 s of the reaction was used as a measure of the luciferase activity. The detector of FB12 luminometer is the 9078B photomultiplier tube (ET Enterprises Ltd, Uxbridge, UK) in photon counting mode with a spectral range of 370–630 nm. It has low and limited sensitivity to red light. Due to the red-shift of bioluminescence spectra at elevated temperatures this can lead

to the artificial diminishing of relative luciferase activity at increased temperatures. Therefore, the activities at different temperatures were corrected for the PMT sensitivity using the bioluminescence spectra at the corresponding temperatures and the quantum efficiency spectral response curve of the PMT.

Bioinformatics

Homology model of the Lml structure was generated previously based on its similarity to *Luciola cruciata* luciferase (Lcl) (Koksharov and Ugarova, 2008). The structure of Lcl in complex with DLSA (PDB: 2D1S) (Nakatsu *et al.*, 2006) was used as a template. The primary homology model was generated using What IF server (Rodriguez *et al.*, 1998). A loop region 183–189 of Lml was modeled using ModLoop server (Fiser and Sali, 2003). This model, its generation details and quality assessment are available in ModelArchive (Tauriello *et al.*, 2025) with the accession code [ma-aleh7](https://www.modelarchive.org/doi/10.5452/ma-aleh7) (<https://www.modelarchive.org/doi/10.5452/ma-aleh7/>). The model quality was estimated using the ModFold9 server (McGuffin and Alharbi, 2024) (Confidence and P-value: CERT, 3.492×10⁻⁵; Global model quality score: 0.9309).

Protein molecular structures were visualized with YASARA View software (Krieger and Vriend, 2014; [RRID:SCR_017591](https://www.yasara.org); www.yasara.org); selected images were then generated with additional use of PovRay 3.6 (www.povray.org).

Results

Screening and selection of thermostable mutants of firefly luciferase

The key part of directed evolution approach is a sensitive and efficient screening procedure. If a simple screen is available, desirable properties can be achieved efficiently, thus making this approach superior to the rational design (Eijsink *et al.*, 2005; Kuchner and Arnold, 1997). Otherwise, screening of libraries may become very laborious and costly. In the case of firefly luciferase, incubation of *E. coli* colonies at elevated temperatures led to the inactivation of insufficiently stable forms of the enzyme. The subsequent photographic detection of *in vivo* bioluminescence of colonies served as a simple method to identify thermostable mutants that displayed higher residual bioluminescence activity. Since the detection of *in vivo* bioluminescence and elevated temperatures used did not kill *E. coli* cells, promising colonies could be picked after the assay directly from the plate screened. Therefore, there was

no need for replica plates during the primary screening of the mutant library. Thus, each round of screening was conducted in a simple and rapid manner. The typical screening of a library of mutant *E. coli* colonies is shown in Supplementary Figure S1.

Table I. Results of random mutagenesis and screening for increased thermostability of *Luciola mingrelica* firefly luciferase

Cycle	Number of clones screened	Ratio of active clones (%)	Incubation temperature before screening (°C)	Thermostable mutants identified [⊗]
1	800	54%	37°C	<u>1T1</u> , 1T2, 1T3
2	900	52%	50°C	<u>2T1</u> , 2T2
3	600	65%	50°C	<u>3T1</u> , 3T2, 3T3
4	1400	65%	55°C	<u>4TS</u> (LmiTS)

[⊗] The most thermostable mutant in each cycle that was used as a parent enzyme for the following cycle is shown in bold and underlined.

Table II. Nucleotide and amino acid substitutions in evolved thermostable mutants

Mutant enzyme	Parent enzyme	Substitutions relative to the parent enzyme	Codon change
1T1	S118C	T213S S364C	acc/agg tct/tgt
1T2 1T3	S118C	silent L294 silent S300 S364A	tta/ttg agt/agg tct/gct
2T1	1T1	silent P135 K156R A217V silent S234 silent A330	cct/ccc aaa/aga gca/gta tca/tcg gct/gca
2T2	1T1	E356V	gaa/gta
3T1 3T2	2T1	C146S E356K	tgt/agg gaa/aaa
3T3	2T1	E356V	gaa/gta
4TS (LmiTS)	3T1	R211L silent R389	cga/cta cga/cgt

However, care should be taken during screening procedure to avoid cross-contamination of the colonies. When the screening assay is performed quickly the cross-contamination is unlikely. We didn't observe it in this work and in our earlier search for the color-shifted mutants (Koksharov and Ugarova, 2008). But the plates should not be allowed to be covered by the screening solution for a prolonged time, because the colonies would start to partially

wash away, causing possible cross-contamination. The subsequent heating of the plates at 50°C helps to effectively remove the remaining liquid from the surface of the plate by evaporation. Spraying of the screening solution on the plate was also reported to be an effective approach to prevent cross-contamination (Lockard *et al.*, 2011).

Fig. 1. *In vivo* bioluminescence of luciferase mutants after incubation of *E. coli* colonies at 50°C for 40 min. The original source image is available in the Supplementary Materials.

Four consecutive rounds of directed evolution were conducted in order to increase thermal stability of Lml. Mutagenesis was applied to a 785 bp gene region coding for amino acid residues 130–390 out of 548 residues of Lml. The mutant S118C was used as a starting point due to its slightly higher thermostability than that of WT (Koksharov and Ugarova, 2008). The most stable mutant in each cycle was used as a parent for the next round of mutagenesis. The main details and results of the four cycles of directed evolution are summarized in Table I. We aimed for a mutation rate of about 1 amino acid change (2–3 base changes) per the region mutated and 30–40% of inactive clones in the library, which is reported to be the most convenient for an efficient selection of beneficial mutations (Cirino *et al.*, 2003). The resultant ratio of inactive clones turned out to be slightly higher as seen from Tables I and II and was suitable for the successful selection of thermostable mutants.

During the first cycle of mutagenesis the mutant colonies were screened for *in vivo* bioluminescence activity directly after growing at 37°C. The insufficient stability of WT Lml at these conditions allowed identifying three clones with increased thermostability (Table I) that led to distinctly brighter colonies. These mutants demonstrated similar level of *in vivo* stability, and their *E. coli* colonies generated similar yellow-green bioluminescence compared to orange-yellow light produced by the parent enzyme S118C (Supplementary

Table III. Biochemical characteristics of purified luciferase enzymes

Enzyme	Relative specific activity* / %		K_M / μ M		λ_{\max} (half-width) / nm		t_{opt} / °C	Half-life / min (42°C, TsB1 buffer)
	Flash-height	Integrated (90 s)	LH ₂	ATP	pH 7.8	pH 6.0		
WT	100 ± 6	100 ± 9	74 ± 8	177 ± 20	566 (78)	616 (79)	25	9.1 ± 0.8
S118C	130 ± 13	116 ± 6	49 ± 4	153 ± 16	566 (75)	616 (82)	n.d.	13.7 ± 0.5
4TS	190 ± 12	216 ± 9	72 ± 8	30 ± 3	573 (92)	609 (91)	37 – 50	592 ± 20

* Specific activity measurements were performed at room temperature as described in Materials and methods.

The values are expressed relative to that of Lml WT defined as 100, which is equivalent to 7.8×10^{12} RLU/s/mg and 6.2×10^{13} RLU/mg for flash height-based and 90 s integration-based assays, respectively.

Figure S2) indicating lower pH-sensitivity of these mutants. During the second and third cycles of mutagenesis an additional incubation at 50°C was needed to detect more thermostable mutants. Figure 1 shows a comparison of *in vivo* thermal stability of the mutants obtained during the first 3 cycles. Three mutants obtained at the third cycle displayed similar bioluminescence brightness after incubation at 50°C but increasing temperature to 55°C revealed higher stability of the mutants 3T1, 3T2 compared with 3T3. The fourth cycle led to the mutant 4TS. When incubating colonies of mutants 4TS and 3T1 at 55°C for 40 min the former retained noticeable brightness of bioluminescence while the latter was completely inactivated. Thus, the mutant 4TS showed the highest *in vivo* thermostability among mutants obtained in this study. Moreover, the colonies of 4TS displayed decreased but noticeable bioluminescence after 20 min at 60°C. At this temperature *E. coli* cells completely lost their viability after 2 min, so the use of replica plates would be required for the selection of mutants with higher thermostability.

It is noteworthy that *in vivo* bioluminescence of the mutant 4TS showed appreciably higher temperature optimum compared with WT. WT firefly luciferases generally have a temperature optimum of activity at 22–25°C (Mortazavi *et al.*, 2008; Seliger and McElroy, 1964). *E. coli* colonies harboring WT Lml, that were treated with luciferin solution to induce bioluminescence and then heated from the room temperature to 37°C, showed a notable decrease of the bioluminescence brightness and at 50°C the bioluminescence became almost unnoticeable. On the contrary, the brightness of the colonies harboring mutant 4TS was notably higher when heating the colonies from the room temperature to 37°C. Upon further heating the colony brightness did not show significant change up to 50°C, and at 55–60°C the bioluminescence began to decrease. The higher temperature optimum of activity was

later confirmed for the purified enzyme.

Sequence analysis

DNA sequences of the 9 mutants selected during the four cycles of directed evolution were determined (Table II). The resultant mutant 4TS contained 8 substitutions compared with WT: S118C (parent enzyme), T213S, K156R, R211L, A217V, C146S, E356K and S364C. The last 7 substitutions appeared in the course of directed evolution. The mutants 1T2, 1T3 and the mutants 3T1, 3T2 turned out to be identical. This is most likely the result of the clone duplication at the stage of bacterial transformation. The substitution E356V appeared during the second and third cycles of mutagenesis but did not result in the most stable mutant at each cycle.

Expression and purification of mutant and WT luciferases

WT Lml and the mutant 4TS were expressed using the pETL7 plasmid, and hence, contained additional N-terminal peptide MASK- and C-terminal peptide -AKM was changed to the sequence -SGPVEHHHHHH. Average yields of the purified proteins (mg/0.2 L) were 32 mg for WT and 60 mg for 4TS. The 1 ml Ni-IDA column was able to bind about 33 mg of luciferase. The purity of the enzymes was more than 95% as estimated by SDS/PAGE. After the purification Lml enzymes were obtained in HB buffer containing 300 mM imidazole, 2 mM EDTA, 1 mM DTT and generally remained fully active for up to 1 month when stored at 4°C. For the long-term storage the proteins were transferred to GF buffer and stored at –80°C. When frozen in GF, luciferase retained full activity for at least 2 years and tolerated several freeze-thaw cycles without inactivation.

The main catalytic and bioluminescent features of the mutant enzymes are presented in Table III. The properties of

Fig. 2. Bioluminescence spectra of WT luciferase and the mutant 4TS at different pH ($t = 25^{\circ}\text{C}$).

the mutant S118C are also included for the comparison. The substitutions in the mutant 4TS led to a 1.9-fold increase in specific activity as well as to 5.7-fold improvement in K_M value for ATP. The mutant 4TS displayed typical flash-like light emission kinetics with the kinetic profile close to that of WT except for a slightly higher decay time that resulted in a slight increase of the integrated specific activity (Supplementary Figure S3).

Bioluminescence spectra

Bioluminescence emission spectra of WT Lml and the mutant 4TS were measured over the pH range from 6.0 to 9.0 at 25°C (Table III, Figure 2). At the pH optimum of 7.8, the mutant 4TS had a wider spectrum in comparison with WT indicating a higher contribution of the red emitter (Figure 2). WT and 4TS showed the classic red-shift (Fraga, 2008; Seliger and McElroy, 1964) of the bioluminescence spectra at acidic pH. Elevated temperatures are known to be another factor leading to the red-shift of the firefly luciferase bioluminescence

Fig. 3. Bioluminescence spectra of WT luciferase and the mutant 4TS at temperatures 10° , 20° , 25° , 37° , 42°C (pH 7.8).

spectra (Seliger and McElroy, 1964). To investigate the effect of temperature on the emission color, bioluminescence spectra were measured at 10, 20, 25, 37 and 42°C at pH 7.8 (Figure 3). Increasing temperature from 25 to 42°C greatly enhanced the contribution of the red emission in the case of both WT and 4TS. Lowering the temperature to 10°C narrowed the spectra of WT and 4TS almost eliminating the contribution of the red emitter in both cases (Figure 3).

Thermostability

First, the thermal stability of 4TS, the mutant S118C and WT Lml was compared at 42°C in Tris-acetate buffer TsB1 (Table III, Figure 4). This buffer solution is close in composition with the typical reagents for the bioluminescent ATP assay (Moroz *et al.*, 2008). Directed evolution has increased the half-life of Lml at 42°C about 65-fold compared to WT. The starting mutant S118C shows the 1.5-fold increase in stability at these conditions so most of the stabilization is due to the seven substitutions obtained during directed evolution. Then

Fig. 4. Thermal inactivation of WT (squares) and 4TS (triangles) in Tris-acetate buffer TsB1 at 37°C (empty symbols) and at 42°C (filled symbols), respectively. The enzyme concentration was 13 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

the thermal inactivation of 4TS and WT has been studied in TsB1 in the range of temperatures from 37° to 55°C. Thermal inactivation of WT and 4TS was also studied in the Naphosphate buffer TsB2 in the same range of temperatures to compare our results with the literature data. The buffer solution similar to TsB2 was used by a number of authors for testing thermostability of luciferase mutants (Kajiyama and Nakano, 1994; Kitayama *et al.*, 2003; White *et al.*, 1996).

At all temperatures studied the thermal inactivation obeyed the first order with the exception of the inactivation in TsB1 buffer at 37°C when both WT and 4TS showed a stage of faster inactivation to 50% (WT) or to 80% (4TS) of activity followed by the stage of slower inactivation (Figure 4). In the case of WT this bend of the inactivation curve was less pronounced.

The constants of thermal inactivation for different temperatures are presented in Supplementary Table S1. The Arrhenius plot for these constants is shown in Figure 5 (the values for the slow stage are presented for 37°C). At all the temperatures studied 4TS was significantly more stable than WT, but elevating the temperature lowered this difference. For example, the half-time of 4TS at 37°C in TsB1 buffer is 158 times greater than that of WT, but the difference decreases to 65 times at 42°C and to 6 times at 50°C. As can be seen from the Arrhenius plot, TsB2 buffer causes significant stabilization of both WT and 4TS compared with TsB1 buffer. But the extent of stabilization also decreases with temperature. The stability of WT luciferase at 37°C is 38 times greater in TsB2

Fig. 5. Arrhenius plot for thermal inactivation of WT (squares) and 4TS (triangles) in buffer TsB1 (filled symbols) and TsB2 (empty symbols). The enzyme concentration was 13 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

buffer compared with TsB1 buffer, but it decreases to only 4 times at 50°C. Thus, the higher starting level of luciferase stability leads to a higher degree of stabilization caused by the mutations in the mutant 4TS or by using the stabilizing TsB2 buffer.

It is noteworthy that even in TsB2 buffer the mutant 4TS loses half of its activity within 1.3 min at 55°C, whereas *in vivo* in *E. coli* colonies it retained appreciable bioluminescence after 20 min at 60°C. Thus, *in vivo* microenvironment provides much higher stabilization of luciferase than buffers typically employed.

Optimum temperature for luciferase activity

The optimum temperature for the activity was estimated for both WT and 4TS (Figure 6). The activity of WT luciferase reached maximum at 25°C and decreased at higher temperatures. The activity of 4TS reaches a plateau at 37–50°C, which is consistent with the *in vivo* observations.

Bioluminescence spectra of the firefly luciferase undergo a red-shift at elevated temperatures that, given the same light output, leads to a decrease of the bioluminescence intensity measured by the luminometer due to a low and limited sensitivity of the PMT at wavelengths higher than 600 nm. Therefore, in the boundary case of monomodal green and red emission the registered activity for the red bioluminescence would be about 4.2 times lower (results not shown). This effect is not important in the case of WT luciferase because the significant changes of its spectra begin when its activity is

already low (Figures 3 and 6). But in the case of 4TS, the correction for the PMT sensitivity was necessary (Figure 6), otherwise the measured maximum of activity was mistakenly observed at 30°C.

Fig. 6. Temperature dependence of the specific activity of WT luciferase and the mutant 4TS. The data were corrected (filled squares ■) or not corrected (empty squares □) for the spectral response of the detector.

Discussion

Thermostability screening

We used the *in vivo* screening procedure to identify thermostable mutants of firefly luciferase directly in *E. coli* colony library. Up to 2000–3000 colonies could be screened on a single 90 mm Petri dish. A cycle of random mutagenesis and screening of 1000 colonies typically results in 1–2 different thermostable mutants. Thus, each round of mutagenesis can be conducted in a simple and rapid manner. The part of the Lml gene coding for amino acid residues 130–390 was targeted for mutagenesis because of the convenient restriction sites and because most reported mutants that enhance the thermostability of firefly luciferases fall within

this region. The four cycles of directed evolution have increased the half-life of Lml 65-fold at 42°C in TsB1 buffer. Moreover, although the intermediate mutants were not checked for the catalytic efficiency, the resultant mutant 4TS showed the significant improvement in specific activity and K_M for ATP.

Further stabilization can be achieved by additional cycles of mutagenesis. In this case the use of replica plates will be required at the colony screening step because the incubation temperature will exceed 60°C making the screening procedure lethal for *E. coli* cells. Also, the remaining C-terminal region (amino acid residues 391–544) of firefly luciferase can be explored because few thermostable mutants are known for this part of the protein: P407T/G396R (M. Koksharov, unpublished results) and F467R (Law *et al.*, 2006).

Structural analysis

The mutant 4TS contained 7 new substitutions compared with its parent form S118C: T213S, K156R, R211L, A217V, C146S, E356K, and S364C. All the substitutions are non-conservative among firefly luciferases. Judging from the order of appearance of these substitutions in the course of directed evolution (Table II), literature data and their location in the 3D structure of the enzyme (Figure 7), four of these substitutions are suggested to be mainly responsible for the increase in thermal stability: R211L, A217V, E356K, and S364C. In the previous studies the mutations of the residues A217 (Kajiyama and Nakano, 1993) and E356 (White *et al.*, 1996) were shown to significantly increase the thermostability of firefly luciferases. Mutations of the residues R211 and S364 are reported for the first time. The thermostabilizing effect of the substitutions R211L, S364C, and S364A can be attributed to the improvement of the internal hydrophobic packing by the substitution of the non-conservative buried polar residues by the hydrophobic ones (Fersht and Serrano, 1993). The mutants C146S (Modestova *et al.*, 2011) and S118C were shown to cause a slight increase in thermal stability (1.3 and 1.5-fold, respectively) at 42°C. Therefore, they may contribute in part to the high thermal stability of 4TS. The surface mutation C146S is also known to increase the resistance to oxidative inactivation (Modestova *et al.*, 2011) and can explain the increased storage stability of 4TS in the absence of DTT compared with WT. The mutants T213S/S364C and S364A displayed similar *in vivo* properties. Thus, it is unlikely that the substitution T213S is accountable for the increase in stability. The substitution of the surface residue 156 from positively

charged Lys to Arg is also unlikely to affect thermostability.

Figure 7 shows the positions of the substitutions of the mutant 4TS in the 3D-structure model of Lml generated by homology modeling using the structure of Lcl (Koksharov and Ugarova, 2008). The luciferase structure consists of 3 distinct subdomains. The subdomains A and B compose the large N-terminal domain of firefly luciferase while the subdomain C is the smaller C-terminal domain. The two domains are connected by a flexible linker loop (Nakatsu *et al.*, 2006). All four presumable key thermostabilizing substitutions (R211L, A217V, E356K, and S364C) are located in the second subdomain of firefly luciferase. Though the larger part of the mutated region belongs to the second subdomain (198 amino acid residues), the fact that thermostabilizing mutations were not found in the last 62 amino acid residues of the first subdomain is consistent with the findings of Frydman and coworkers who had investigated the unfolding of firefly luciferase by chemical denaturation with subsequent protease treatment (Frydman *et al.*, 1999). The authors have shown that the fragments comprising residues 1–190 and 422–544 possess high intrinsic stability. These fragments mainly correspond to the subdomains A and C of firefly luciferase. The middle subdomain B (192–435) was shown to be significantly less stable and was the first to unfold under denaturing conditions. Thus, it may be concluded that the stability of the second subdomain is the main factor that determines the stability of the firefly luciferase protein. Therefore, most of the thermostabilizing mutations should be located in the second subdomain or in an interface between the second subdomain and the other two subdomains. It is noteworthy that almost all thermostable mutants reported in the literature are located in this part of the luciferase structure. The mutant S118C is located at the interface between the subdomains A and B.

Due to the presence of the 8 substitutions in 4TS, it is unclear what mutations contribute to the significant decrease of the K_M for ATP, and further mutagenesis experiments are required to definitely answer this question. In contrast to the other substitutions in 4TS, the residue S364 is located near the adenosine moiety of ATP (Figure 7). Therefore, the substitution S364C may be one of the main factors responsible for the decrease of K_M for ATP. The substitution S118C causes a slight decrease of K_M for ATP (Table III). It is located away from ATP molecule near the residues participating in binding of Mg^{2+} and the phosphate moiety of ATP. The substitutions A217L, E354K in Ppl (Tisi

et al., 2002) and C146S in Lml (Modestova *et al.*, 2011) did not change the K_M for ATP according to the literature, so the corresponding mutations are less likely to contribute to the improvement of K_M of the mutant 4TS.

Fig. 7. Homology model of Lml showing the location of substitutions in the mutant 4TS.

Four key thermostabilizing mutations are underlined. LO and AMP – luciferyl and adenylate groups of DLSA (5'-O-[N-(dehydrolyciferyl)-sulfamoyl] adenosine). Subdomains A, B and C are depicted in blue, grey and orange, respectively. This model and the corresponding YASARA scene file (.sce) of this figure are available at ModelArchive (accession # [ma-aleh7](#)).

Bioluminescence spectra

Bioluminescence spectrum is a key feature of luciferase enzymes. Most firefly luciferases demonstrate highly pH-sensitive bioluminescence spectra that undergo a large shift from green to red region upon lowering pH from alkaline to acidic. Red-shifts are also observed at elevated temperatures and increased concentration of divalent heavy metal ions (Seliger and McElroy, 1964). This red shift is attributed to the switching between two different molecular forms of the product (green and red emitters) (Fraga, 2008). In some cases mutants that significantly increase thermostability also lead to a low pH-sensitivity of the bioluminescence spectra (Kitayama *et al.*, 2003; Law *et al.*, 2006). The thermostable mutant 4TS

displays broadened and pH-sensitive bioluminescence spectra, thus confirming that generally thermostability and pH-sensitivity are independent. The broadened bioluminescence spectrum of 4TS and its narrowing at low temperatures indicate that the microenvironment of the emitter in the active site became more flexible in spite of the increase of the overall protein stability.

The broadening of the spectra may be attributed to the effect of the substitutions A217V and E354K which were shown to increase the ratio of red emitter in case of Lml (Koksharov and Ugarova, 2011) or Hpl (Kitayama *et al.*, 2003), Ppl (White *et al.*, 1996) and *Lampyrus turkestanicus* luciferase (Alipour *et al.*, 2009) respectively. In contrast, the mutation S364C counteracts the broadening of the spectra by decreasing the contribution of the red emitter (Supplementary Figure S2).

Comparison of the thermostability of the mutant 4TS with the previous studies

The mutant 4TS developed in this study appears to be one of most stable firefly luciferase variants available. Its stability was significantly higher than that of the recently developed multi-point thermostable mutant of Ppl (half-time of 129 h for Lml versus 11.5 h for Ppl at 37°C in the buffers with a moderate ionic strength) which represents the thermostable version of the most widely used firefly luciferase (Branchini *et al.*, 2007). The stability of 4TS also surpasses the stability of the thermostable mutant E356R/V368A of Hpl (half-life of 33.4 h versus 3.5 h at 45°C in the buffer TsB2) (Kitayama *et al.*, 2003) and the mutant T217V of Lcl (half-life of 44 min versus 28 min at 50°C in the buffer TsB2) (Kajiyama and Nakano, 1993). However, the mutant *Luciola lateralis* luciferase with the substitution A217L shows greater stability (half-life of 125 min at 50°C in the buffer TsB2) than the mutant 4TS owing to the fact that WT *Luciola lateralis* luciferase is naturally the most thermostable among WT firefly luciferases (Kajiyama and Nakano, 1994). The 28-point mutant of *Photuris pennsylvanica* luciferase developed in Promega Corp. (Wood and Hall, 1999) still remains the most thermostable variant of firefly luciferase to date. The conduction of additional cycles of directed evolution and the introduction of additional mutations is needed for the further increase of Lml thermostability.

Conclusions

We demonstrated that the *in vivo* directed evolution strategy is

a simple and efficient approach to increase firefly luciferase thermostability without sacrificing catalytic efficiency. In fact, the resultant mutant displayed superior catalytic properties: increased specific activity, lower K_M for ATP and increased temperature optimum.

In typical applications, for example, ATP measurement or as a reporter gene, firefly luciferase is usually used at temperatures up to 37°C. The mutant LmiTS (4TS) retains 70% activity after two days of incubation at 37°C. Thus, its stability is sufficient for most common *in vivo* and *in vitro* applications. The improved protein yield, specific activity and catalytic efficiency of the mutant 4TS make it an efficient tool for ATP determination (Ugarova *et al.*, 2010). The increased temperature optimum of 4TS can be advantageous for *in vivo* imaging and high temperature applications. The non-lethal *in vivo* screening approach described in the present study can potentially be adapted to other beetle or non-beetle luciferases when the increased level of thermal stability is desirable.

End Matter

Supplementary Data

This article contains supporting information (Supplementary Materials: Figures S1–S4 and Table S1) integrated after the end of the main manuscript text.

Author Contributions & Notes

M.K. & N.N. conceived the study. M.K. designed research, performed experiments, analyzed data and wrote the paper. M.K. & N.N. edited the paper. N.N. supervised the project and obtained funding.

We declare no conflict of interest.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary Figures and Tables

Fig. S1. Typical screening of the 90 mm plate with mutant *E. coli* colonies for thermostability (second cycle of random mutagenesis). *In vivo* bioluminescence before (a) and after (b) incubation of the plate at 50°C. The thermostable mutant 2T1 is marked by the arrow. Green bioluminescence of most of the colonies is due to the presence of the Y35N mutation in the cloning vector used at 2nd–4th cycles.

Fig. S2. *In vivo* bioluminescence of *E. coli* XL1-blue colonies expressing the luciferase mutants 1T1–1T3 and their parent enzyme S118C. Bioluminescence was induced after the growth of cells at 37°C.

Table S1. Constants of irreversible thermal inactivation of WT Lml and the mutant 4TS at 37–55°C

Enzyme	Buffer	k_{in}, h^{-1}					
		37°C	42°C	45°C	47°C	50°C	55°C
WT	TsB1	0.95 (to 50%) 0.58 (further)	4.57	15.1	n.d. ¹⁾	68	n.d.
	TsB2	0.02	0.73	3.27	n.d.	18.6	n.d.
4TS	TsB1	0.04 (to 80%) 0.0037 (further)	0.07	0.95	2.83	11.1	99
	TsB2	n.d.	n.d.	0.021	0.047	0.94	31
$k_{in}(WT)$	TsB1	168	65	16	-	6	-
$k_{in}(4TS)$	TsB2	-	-	155	-	20	-

¹⁾ n.d. – not determinedNote: The error associated with k_{in} falls within 10% of the value.**Fig. S3.** Normalized light emission kinetic profiles of WT Lml and the mutant 4TS. Each curve is a mean of 6 (WT) or 8 (4TS) measurements. Flash heights and integrated intensities were within 10% of the mean value. Reactions were conducted at the saturating concentrations of the substrates as described in Materials and Methods. The final reaction mixture contained 2×10^{-6} mg/ml luciferase, 0.15 mM LH_2 and 1.2 mM ATP in 50 mM Tris-acetate (pH 7.8) buffer containing 10 mM $MgSO_4$ and 2 mM EDTA.

Back of the plate with an agar segment (colonies are marked with their designations)

Colonies on agar: under the ambient light

Bioluminescence in the dark

Fig. S4. The original image, which was used to produce the Figure 1 in the main text. *In vivo* bioluminescence of luciferase mutants after incubation of *E. coli* colonies at 50°C for 40 min. The luciferase mutants S118C, 1T1, 2T1, 3T1–3T3 were photographed in the dark with the following settings: 10 seconds exposure, F 2.6, focal length 5.8 mm. The designations of mutants marked on the plate correspond (→) to the ones used in the paper as follows: MT8 → S118C, 3M → 1T, 4T → 2T, 5T → 3T.

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